

Trustworthy data-centric geotechnics

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ABSTRACT

There are two major technology related changes that are widely viewed as seismic. One is the emergence of artificial intelligence (AI) that is close to passing the Turing test. The second is the introduction of the first AI Act in the European Union (EU). The former portends business opportunities that are too large to ignore in all industries. The latter mandates businesses to manage risks appropriately depending on the impact of AI systems on individuals and society. Machine learning (ML) and AI are at most deployed as proofs of concept in geotechnics. This perspectives article advocates a greater appetite for data-driven innovations in practice to take advantage of major breakthroughs occurring elsewhere. Besides the obvious benefits to practice and to the stakeholders that we serve, embracing data-centric geotechnics is the only way for geotechnical engineers to remain in the driver seat to deploy ML/AI responsibly and safely. This agenda to introduce trustworthiness explicitly in research and practice is called “trustworthy data-centric geotechnics”. Pockets of preliminary research that relate to trustworthiness are highlighted.

Introduction

An analysis of the construction technology ecosystem by McKinsey Capital Projects & Infrastructure identified three constellations of connected solutions that are expected to gain the most traction in the near future (Blanco et al., 2018). One of them is “artificial intelligence and analytics”. Blanco et al. (2018) noted that “the potential impact is so large that the industry can no longer afford to ignore it. AI methods are increasingly able to work across industries, elevating the threat of competition from nontraditional market entrants”. Over the past few years, research in data-centric geotechnics has been accelerating as a result of tremendous advances in machine learning (ML) and artificial intelligence (AI) in conjunction with automation and connectivity. OpenAI o3, DeepSeek R1, Deepmind Gemini, Meta AI Llama, Anthropic Claude, Baidu Ernie, Alibaba Qwen 2.5, ByteDance Doubao and other generative AIs have moved the *cognitive* divide between what a machine can do and what a human can do in a major way. 2023 is regarded as a breakout year for generative AIs (GAI) (McKinsey, 2023a). Nvidia CEO predicted that AI could pass all human tests in five years (Nellis, 2024). OpenAI o3 and DeepSeek R1 have electrified the AI community on whether artificial general intelligence (AGI) is within reach (Jones, 2025). OpenAI CEO Sam Altman opined in his personal blog: “We are now confident we know how to build AGI as we have traditionally understood it” (Koetsier, 2025). There is near complete consensus that ML and AI have the potential to transform the way we work, live, and play in many fundamental and unexpected ways. However, there is no consensus on how fast and how many jobs would be transformed (Gordon, 2024;

Ma, 2024). Nonetheless, the author argues that it is more prudent for geotechnical engineers to start understanding and exploring the power and the impact of emerging digital technologies, particularly their value propositions to practice (benefits) and the responsible use of AI (risks). The European Union (EU)’s AI Act defines 4 categories of risk for AI systems as shown in Fig. 1. AI systems for geotechnics is classified as “high risk” because they could be deployed in “critical infrastructures (e.g. transport), that could put the life and health of citizens at risk”. These AI systems are subject to regulations and far-reaching obligations under Art. 6–51 of the EU AI Act. With the introduction of this landmark bill, the author argues that it is more prudent to overreact than to underreact to this change that is still unfolding rapidly, be it gradual or disruptive.

The International Symposium on Machine Learning and Big Data in Geoscience was initiated by the ISSMGE Technical Committee of Machine Learning & Big Data (TC309). The first event was held at the Norwegian Geotechnical Institute, Oslo, Norway, 21–22 Oct 2018 and the most recent event (fourth) was held at University College Cork, Ireland, 29 Aug - 1 Sep 2023. A discussion panel was held before the second event (Tongji University, Shanghai, China, 28–30 Jul 2019) [ISSMGE Bulletin 13(4), 2019, 8–14]. This discussion has evolved to a series of Machine Learning in Geotechnics Dialogue (MLIGD) – the fourth was held at the Okayama Convention Center, Okayama, Japan on 5 Dec 2023 (Leung et al., 2024). The third and fourth dialogue were thematic, namely data-driven site characterization (Phoon et al., 2023a) and ML supremacy projects (Leung et al., 2024), respectively. The fifth dialogue took place recently on 13 October 2024 in conjunction with

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Fig. 1. Risk categories according to EU AI Act. (Source: https://www.ey.com/en_ch/forensic-integrity-services/the-eu-ai-act-what-it-means-for-your-business).

the Second Workshop on Future of Machine Learning in Geotechnics (www.fomlig2024.com). The theme is *secure* data sharing which involves prioritizing data security and privacy.

An attempt to explore the future of ML in geotechnics (MLIG) was made in 2023 (Phoon & Zhang, 2023), but many research papers have been published since then as an indicator of the rate of progress. Phoon and Zhang (2023) proposed a simple classification scheme for ML based on its value to practice: (1) Type 1 (incremental value) involving available data and existing conventional applications, (2) Type 2a (potentially high value) involving available data and new applications, (3) Type 2b (high value) involving new data and existing applications, and (4) Type 3 (disruptive value) involving new data and completely novel applications (e.g., precision construction, autonomous construction control, physical AI, forecasting using large language models, collaborative robots). These Type 3 examples are meant to illustrate applications that are outside the reach of current *non-AI* technologies. No Type 3 ML/AI has emerged thus far. This reflects the nascent state of adoption of AI in practice. Note that the existing body of work on geotechnical reliability (Chwała et al., 2023; Phoon, 2023) can be mapped into this classification scheme as Type 0, because there is no “learning” capacity in classical reliability methods. “No learning capacity” describes a limitation that has largely gone unnoticed in a non-AI method, namely it can only be improved by a human. This refers to all current methods in geotechnical engineering. However, all humans can improve themselves – an advantage that is unique to human learning until recently. Advanced AIs can now improve themselves directly using big data and even more recently using test-time compute in contrast to conventional non-AI models that require human-in-the-loop to develop better physics-based models. The purpose of this *perspectives* article is to introduce a sample of the recent volume of work and to point to major breakthroughs occurring elsewhere that can result in the emergence of Type 3 applications to support data-driven decision making in geotechnical engineering practice. This article argues for a more balanced development of ML/AI systems that considers both value and risk under a new framing called “trustworthy data-centric geotechnics”. Pockets of preliminary research that relate to trustworthiness are highlighted. The introduction of “trustworthy data-centric geotechnics” will hopefully attract researchers to address this critical trustworthiness issue in a more comprehensive way.

Data-centric geotechnics

Phoon et al. (2022a) argued that research in ML/AI should be framed under a more holistic “data first practice central” agenda called data-centric geotechnics. The purpose is to start a conversation on whether everything must be understood from “first princi-

ples” which is physics way of looking at the world (Phoon, 2020a). In this paradigm, data is only valuable as a set of inputs to a physics model. Two companion special issues in Georisk have been published in issue 17, volume 1 (Machine learning and AI in geotechnics, 12 papers) (Phoon et al., 2023b) and issue 18, volume 1 (Data-centric geotechnics for practice, 16 papers) (Phoon et al., 2024a). In addition, one special issue in Underground Space (Machine learning and AI for underground metaverse, 11 papers, <https://www.sciencedirect.com/special-issue/10HDT8RD87H>) (Phoon et al., 2024b) and in Computers and Geotechnics (Recent advancements in data-centric geotechnics, 24 papers, <https://www.sciencedirect.com/special-issue/107KB6917M5>) (Phoon et al., 2024c) have been published. One special issue in Soils and Foundations (Machine Learning in Geotechnics, 9 papers, <https://www.sciencedirect.com/special-issue/106JZ159T84>) is under preparation. The total number of papers appearing in these 5 special issues is 72 over a period of 2 years. This list of special issues is not intended to be comprehensive. The interested reader can refer to other sources such as <https://www.issmge.org/committees/technical-committees/impact-on-society/machine-learning>. However, it does indicate the rapidly expanding interest in the research community.

The first workshop on the Future of Machine Learning in Geotechnics (FOMLIG) was successfully held on 5–6 Dec 2023, Okayama, Japan (Phoon & Shuku, 2024). Significant gaps in research were identified such as privacy-enhancing technologies (PETs) and trustworthy AI. The second workshop (2FOMLIG) was held in Chengdu, 11–13 Oct 2024. The impact of large language models such as ChatGPT was explored in 2FOMLIG likely for the first time in geotechnical engineering. The FOMLIG Council was launched during 2FOMLIG to advance trustworthy data-centric geotechnics in research, practice, and regulation (<https://www.fomlig.com/>). The third workshop (3FOMLIG) would be held in Florence, 15–17 Oct 2025. The theme of 3FOMLIG is centered on “how current and forthcoming synergies between human and AI will foster geotechnical research, practice, and education, and how human conscience and ethics can best nurture this partnership through new paradigms, cultural perceptions, and regulations” (<https://fomlig2025.com/>). A geotechnical multiagent hackathon would be held in 3FOMLIG. A multiagent system consists of multiple interacting AIs.

Although research in data-centric geotechnics is in its infancy, its value to practice has been demonstrated in the current body of work. The value of ML to practice was the focus of the Fourth Machine Learning in Geotechnics Dialogue (4MLIGD) (Leung et al., 2024). Phoon and Zhang (2023) defined ML supremacy projects as “those involving large complex datasets (perhaps real time data) from multiple sources covering large spatial domains that cannot be handled effectively and efficiently using conventional methods and there is a strong demand for implementation of ML methods in these projects”. However, these projects are not Type 3 that are conjectured to make “practice unrecognizable by present day engineers” (Phoon et al., 2025a).

Data-centric geotechnics is distinctive from other fields in geotechnical engineering and ML (Phoon et al., 2022a). It is an emerging interdisciplinary field that involves the integration of information, data, techniques, tools, perspectives, concepts, theories, and/or experiences from geotechnical engineering and ML. Numerous foundational challenges beyond methodological ones can be identified when research is pursued under a more holistic data-centric geotechnics agenda covering the following three elements:

- (1) Data centrality. Databases are also called Big Indirect Data (BID) because they are not directly applicable to any specific site. For site data, there are at least seven data attributes common to BIDs that are frequently presented as a mnemonic in the literature, MUSIC-3X (Multivariate, Uncertain and Unique, Sparse, Incomplete, and potentially Corrupted with “3X” denoting 3D spatial variability). There are additional data attributes such as geologic uncertainty (“G”). Spatial variability generally refers to soil prop-

Fig. 2. Trustworthy data-centric geotechnics with trust as its core (presented in 2023 Harry Poulos Award and Lecture, Sydney, 10 July 2024, <https://australiangeomechanics.org/meetings/databases-and-data-centric-geotechnics/>).

erties that change from point to point in a soil mass – data is numerical (continuous). Geologic uncertainty refers to distribution of soil types or anomalies – data is categorical (nominal). Data-centricity requires MUSIC-3X-G or more complex data attributes to be addressed directly rather than simplifying it to fit the ideal assumptions in classical statistics. The case to grow larger, richer (multimodal sense), and different types of databases to drive the development of data-centric geotechnics is very compelling. One well known example in computer vision is ImageNet. The ISSMGE database sharing initiative 304dB is far less mature than ImageNet (Ching & Phoon, 2025).

- (2) Fit for (and transform) practice. It is not sufficient to demonstrate that a proposed data-driven method is effective in principle based on a “toy” problem with ideal data. For example, true scale 3D benchmark examples are posed to highlight data-driven site characterization challenges (Phoon et al., 2022b). OpenAI o3 caused a stir recently because it excelled in a benchmark test called ARC-AGI that is based on the Abstract Reasoning Corpus. It is also necessary to show that the computational cost is reasonable. For example, Settle3 has adopted the Gaussian Process Regression (Ching et al., 2023) to generate a complete subsurface profile based on typical CPT layouts for settlement analysis (<https://www.rocsience.com/software/settle3#latest-features>). Settle3 is a 3D settlement and foundation software that provides an analysis of soil settlement and consolidation under foundations, and liquefaction analysis.
- (3) Geotechnical context. Site recognition is related to a fundamental feature in geotechnical practice, namely all sites are different to some extent (site specificity) (Phoon & Ching, 2022; Phoon et al., 2025b). Hence, a database containing data from multiple sites is BID. The challenge is to quantify “site uniqueness”, directly or indirectly, so that sparse site-specific data can be supplemented by BID to produce a quasi-site-specific model that is more unbiased than a generic model and less uncertain than a site-specific model. The concept of site uniqueness is related to the site feature of interest (can be scientific or engineering). Only multivariate soil or rock properties have been studied as a feature of interest thus far in geotechnical engineering. Site uniqueness in terms of spatial variability and geologic uncertainty has received limited attention. Site uniqueness in terms of the performance of geotechnical structures has not been conceptualized. Another geotechnical context is staged construction. It has been exploited to improve the prediction of wall deflection in a deep excavation (Tabarrokhi et al., 2024). Interest in combining site characterization information with performance information collected during staged construction to guide decision making in real time is emerging rapidly. This new research area is called machine learning guided observational method (MLOM) (Phoon et al., 2025a).

A pro-active approach to address the potential data security and privacy risks enhances the trust and confidence of the users and stakeholders. Privacy-enhancing technologies (PETs) should be incorporated into the ML solutions from the earliest stages of design, and throughout the entire lifecycle of the system or application. To the authors’ knowledge, this privacy enhancement has not been considered in data-centric geotechnics although Phoon et al. (2024b) suggested expanding the original “data first practice central” agenda in data-centric geotechnics to “data first, practice central, and privacy enhanced”. This article argues that privacy enhancement is only one element of trustworthy AI. In fact, trustworthiness should be regarded as a bedrock that all AI systems classified as high risk in the EU AI Act should be founded on (Choudhuri, 2024). As such, our industry should advocate for “trustworthy data-centric geotechnics” with trustworthiness at its core rather than one element of its agenda (Fig. 2). AI systems are deemed trustworthy if they meet certain requirements such as human agency and oversight, technical robustness and safety, privacy and data governance, transparency, and accountability (High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence, 2019).

In this section, two milestones that contribute to trustworthiness are noteworthy. Fig. 2 marks one of the earliest attempts to recognize the issue of trust in data-centric geotechnics explicitly. The paper by Murakami et al. (2025) published in Volume 1, Issue 1 of Geodata and AI marks the first attempt to bring privacy-enhancing technologies (PETs) to geotechnical engineering. In addition, one research example on “explainability” deserves mention. The Hierarchical Bayesian Model (HBM) is one solution to the site recognition challenge, because it can model inter-site variability (Ching et al., 2021). However, HBM is not “explainable” – the engineer does not know which sites in the database are relevant and how relevant to decision making at the target site. Therefore, an engineer cannot apply “reality checks” on HBM results. Such a “black box” inference method diminishes trustworthiness. Recent clustering solutions are explainable, because the database sites contributing to the inference are identified explicitly (Sharma et al., 2023; Cai et al., 2024a).

Data

Data is now considered to be an asset that is as valuable as our physical infrastructure (Phoon, 2020a). However, this value remains underappreciated by most geotechnical engineers, although it is pivotal to digital transformation. Engineers continue to see the value of data primarily in relation to physics. ML and AI universally depend on data for training, validation, and inference. ISSMGE TC304 has initiated a database sharing project in called 304 dB (<http://140.112.12.21/issmge/tc304.htm>) in 2017 (Ching & Phoon, 2025). The largest collection of geotechnical databases to date was published in 2025: www.routledge.com/9781032578958 (Phoon & Tang, 2025) and www.routledge.com/9781032579108 (Tang & Phoon, 2025) (Fig. 3). Three

Databases for Data-Centric Geotechnics

Site Characterization

Databases for Data-Centric Geotechnics

Geotechnical Structures

Fig. 3. Databases containing site characterization data and performance data of geotechnical structures.

new journals have been launched in 2024: Geodata and AI (GEOAI), Elsevier, Machine Learning and Data Science in Geotechnics (MLaG), ICE Publishing, and Intelligent Geoengineering (IGE), Chinese Society of Rock Mechanics and Engineering (CSRME) and KeAi Publishing. GEOAI covers all geo-related disciplines that need to address the unique challenges in our datasets and hence the unique opportunities to develop novel methods, processes, and systems to transform our research and practice. Discovering the geodata estate is a major focus of GEOAI. The journal also encourages the publication of review/foresight papers, GEOAI benchmark examples (Cai & Phoon, 2025; Phoon et al., 2022c), short communications (Ching & Phoon, 2025), and perspectives from leaders in our community as exemplified by the current paper (Phoon et al., 2025c). MLaG covers the application of ML, AI, big data analysis, and statistical approaches to geotechnical challenges. IGE promotes research at the intersection of geotechnical engineering and intelligent technologies. This list of new journals is not comprehensive. One example is the Intelligent Transportation Infrastructure (Southwest Jiaotong University and Oxford University Press) launched in 2022.

Karpatne et al. (2018) presented nine commonly encountered attributes of geoscience data that should be accounted for in the design of ML algorithms: (1) spatial-temporal structure, (2) heterogeneity in space and time, (3) high dimensionality, (4) lack of concise object definitions, (5) rare classes, (6) multi-source multi-resolution data, (7) poor quality of data, (8) small sample size, and (9) paucity of ground truth. ties to develop novel methods, processes, and systems to transform our research and practice. Phoon (2020b) posed the challenge of drawing insights from large heterogeneous data from many sites (data rich) for decision making at one target site (data poor). He called this the “Goldilocks dilemma”. As noted above, Phoon et al. (2025a) generalized site data attributes from MUSIC-3X to 4S (Site generalizations, Spatial features, Sampling characteristics, and Smart data). It is important to point out developments in vision-language-action (VLA) models such as Robotic Transformer 2 (RT-2) by Deepmind that learns from both web

and robotics data, and translates this knowledge into instructions for robotic control. AI is now capable of learning from data produced by interaction with the real world. AI-on-demand defines “physical AI” as the use of “AI techniques to solve problems that involve direct interaction with the physical world, e.g., by observing the world through sensors or by modifying the world through actuators. The data is generated from various sources, including physical sensors and ‘human sources’, such as social networks or smartphones. Actuation may range from support to human decisions to managing automated devices (e.g., traffic lights, gates) and actively directing autonomous cars, drones, etc.” (<https://www.ai4europa.eu/research/areas/physical-ai>).

In this section, one research example that relates to trustworthiness is noteworthy. As the volume of data increases and the attributes of multi-modal data become more complex, more sophisticated outlier detection methods are needed. Classical outlier detection methods do not work for MUSIC data. Ching et al. (2024) was the first to solve this problem. This research milestone is significant, because it can be applied to screening “bad” data from a database. Trust is diminished when ML/AI is applied without addressing a natural concern best described by the adage “garbage in garbage out”. It is economically infeasible to deploy engineers to screen big complex databases for bad data and arguably impossible because no one accumulates an experience base that covers all data in all countries (Yang et al., 2024). If a MUSIC outlier detection method is available, this screening can be carried out easily by removing one site from a database at a time and checking whether this isolated site is an outlier relative to the database. “Bad” data is defined as any data that misleads the decision maker (Phoon et al., 2023a). It is worse than no data. Phoon et al. (2023a) interpreted the “C” attribute in MUSIC as referring to bad data. Ching et al. (2024) clarified that bad data is relative to the decision at hand. It can be wrong/fake data. In this case, it is bad for all decisions and all target sites. However, it can be irrelevant data. In this case, it is bad only for a particular decision at a particular target site. As far as decision making is concerned, the labels “bad”,

“irrelevant”, or “corrupted” are not important. Cai et al. (2024b) proposed a second MUSIC outlier detection method based on a modified inter-dataset similarity measure (MIDSM). No outlier detection method exists for MUSIC-3X-G or more complex attributes.

Possible futures

The keyword “machine learning” did not appear in the New Millennium Report (National Research Council, 2006) or the Future of Geotechnical Engineering Report (Mitchell & Kopmann, 2013), in part because interest only grew exponentially after the spectacular defeat of top human Go players by a computer program called AlphaGo in 2016. By now, the power of a generative AI such as OpenAI o3 and DeepSeek R1 is evident. Mitchell and Kopmann (2013) already recognized that “information technology (IT) has had a very high impact on many facets of geotechnical engineering” but opined that “while advances in information technology will provide practicing engineers with more information, in the coming years we will see an increasing need for ever more competent engineers who are able to efficiently sift through this ever increasing mound of information and apply good engineering judgment to effectively utilize it”. It suffices to note here that research in human-machine teaming is directed to developing “trustworthy” machines rather than refining the current role of engineering judgment (Assaad & Boshuijzen-Van Burken, 2023; Cominelli et al., 2021; Shayesteh & Jebelli, 2022). Microsoft’s Copilot is an example of what human-machine teaming looks like. Mitchell and Kopmann (2013) raised the challenge of an “information overload” on engineers but the authors did not follow their prescient observation to its logical conclusion, namely it is humanly impossible to make sense of big data directly as it gets to be really big (say yottabyte scale in the near future) and really complex. Trustworthiness is an issue if one accepts the premise that an engineer needs a machine companion in decision making in the future. Interestingly, uncertainty quantification is regarded as important to trustworthiness, because it improves transparency, which is a minimum requirement of traceability. An AI that provides a deterministic answer is likely “over-confident” and wrong. Current designs based on deterministic finite element analyses are feasible because an engineer can review a few input parameters based on experience and interpret the output parameters based on casual understanding. Uncertainty is implicitly recognized in the decision-making process (Phoon et al., 2022d). This deterministic work around is not feasible when the input parameters are very large and very complex (and possibly multi-modal) and the AI model is not interpretable. The author submits that a *probabilistic answer is necessary for ML/AI solutions* in the presence of scarce data which is almost always the case in geotechnical engineering. “Hallucinations” exist when the prediction provided by ML/AI is different from reality. It is rarely emphasized that this condition exists because a deterministic prediction is made. If a deterministic geotechnical ML/AI is adopted, it is nearly certain that some predictions would be “hallucinations”. This would undermine the trust in ML/AI. No engineer will use a geotechnical ML/AI that “hallucinates” occasionally for decision making where human safety is at stake. This serious issue can be mitigated by providing a range of predictions (probabilistic predictions) and to leave the engineer to make a final risk-informed decision that has always been the indispensable remit of a professional engineer. Engineering judgment (that allows uncertainty to be circumvented) is effectively an intuitive “human-machine teaming” method, but it needs a fundamental review if geotechnical decisions are primarily data-driven. Engineering judgment is ineffective for large complex databases and in the absence of casual understanding. In short, trustworthy data-centric geotechnics is intrinsically probabilistic in the foreseeable future. Two research papers with relevance to trustworthiness are noteworthy, because probabilistic ML is outside mainstream research. Ching and Phoon, 2019 were the first to propose a Bayesian ML that quantifies uncertainty rigorously and is computationally feasible for a typical large 3D ground volume. Their method forms the foundation to build an efficient Hierarchical

Bayesian Model (Ching et al., 2021) and probabilistic atoms for dictionary learning (Cai et al., 2025).

Phoon and Shuku (2024) pointed out two useful directions for ML in geotechnics: (1) the potential for an AI to act as an intelligent companion to an engineer in decision making is exciting (McKinsey, 2023b; Murgia, 2024). But for human-machine teaming to be effective, a deliberate approach is needed to build trust between the human and the AI/robot partner and (2) the geotechnical engineering industry that produces and owns the data needs to collaborate with academia to pilot test ML/AI solutions in the real world and to co-develop frameworks with government authorities on data management and other governance matters related to standards/regulations/ethics that will engender trust among the key stakeholders of the built environment. As mentioned above, “trustworthy data-centric geotechnics” is the responsible response to the EU AI Act. Some concrete proposals deserving of further consideration are: (1) development of a “Trusted copilot” for geotechnical design and (2) set standards for the development and responsible use of ML/AI in design and construction. There is an urgency for our community to act, because the EU AI Act is expected to be fully in force two years after its approval by EU Council (Browne, 2024).

The “Copilot” idea is similar to the “Super engineer” idea hypothesized in Phoon et al. (2022b): “A true ‘learning’ algorithm should be able to improve itself. This is distinct from the methods covered in this paper, where predictions are made by ‘learning’ from the data but the methods do not have the capacity to change and improve themselves. Specifically, the predictions may improve with data, but the methods do not improve from more data and from interactions with the engineers. In principle, an AI that can mimic human learning can be regarded as a ‘super engineer’ that has gained and continues to gain from the pooled experiences of all human engineers around the world. Since it is already known that an experienced engineer makes better judgment than a novice with no experience, one can speculate that such a ‘super engineer’ with access to extensive databases, capable of detecting site differences through data-driven methods (as demonstrated in this paper), and capable of moderating its predictions by drawing upon relevant past human experiences will be making better site-specific predictions than those from classical statistical methods moderated by ‘reality checks’ from a single engineer”. One can imagine training an AI on the entire geotechnical literature such as the ISSMGE Online Library (<https://www.issmge.org/publications/online-library>) and other open access publications.

To measure the progress of automation that includes data-driven decision making in geotechnics, one useful reference is the six-level framework proposed by the Society of Automotive Engineers (SAE) that has since been adopted by the U.S. Department of Transportation. The six levels are: Level 0 – no automation; Level 1 – driver assistance; Level 2 – partial automation (“hands off”); Level 3 – conditional automation (“eyes off”); Level 4 – high automation (“mind off”); Level 5 – full automation (“driver off”). From Level 0 to 2, the human monitors the driving environment. From Level 3 to 5, the automated system monitors the driving environment. The geotechnical engineering industry is at most situated at Level 1. At the current rate of technological changes unfolding across industries such as autonomous vehicles, it is not far-fetched to imagine autonomous construction achieving Level 3 in less than one decade through customization of technologies developed elsewhere for geotechnical engineering.

Lastly, the AI revolution is poised to ignite a robotics revolution. Gibney (2024) explained that the “idea is to imbue robots with common-sense knowledge, letting them tackle a wide range of tasks. Many researchers think that robots could become really good, really fast. ‘We believe we are at the point of a step change in robotics,’ says Gerard Andrews, a marketing manager focused on robotics at technology company Nvidia in Santa Clara, California, which in March 2024 launched a general-purpose AI model designed for humanoid robots. This general-purpose foundation model for humanoid robots is called GR00T (short for “Generalist Robot 00 Technology”) (Ackerman, 2024). The EU AI

Act defines a foundation model as an "AI model that is trained on broad data at scale, is designed for generality of output, and can be adapted to a wide range of distinctive tasks". The term "foundation model" in AI should not be confused with the familiar reference to "foundation engineering". At the same time, robots could help to improve AI. Many researchers hope that bringing an embodied experience to AI training could take them closer to the dream of "artificial general intelligence" — AI that has human-like cognitive abilities across any task. "The last step to true intelligence has to be physical intelligence," says Akshara Rai, an AI researcher at Meta in Menlo Park, California" (Gibney, 2024). Despite Nvidia CEO's prediction that "everything is going to be robotic" (Morris, 2024), the jury is still out on robots replacing human workers on a large scale in the near future. Nonetheless, it is possible for robots to take over some dangerous and undesirable tasks. The startup Figure AI was founded in 2022 to develop a general-purpose robot called Figure 01 to alleviate manpower shortages in manufacturing, shipping and logistics, warehousing, and retail (Palmer, 2024). Another example is Unitree's H1 humanoid robot. Construction is possibly not an immediate target industry, because its operating environment is more complex. However, there is no fundamental obstacle to adoption of humanoid robots in the future. For construction equipment manufacturers, this space is worth watching.

Responsible innovation

The value of data has been demonstrated in many industries, particularly in the context of training generative AIs. It is unlikely that geotechnical engineering is an exception in this sea change. However, it is recognized that the data attributes in geo-related disciplines are complex (e.g., MUSIC-3X-G) and there is a paucity of ground truth for training a *foundation AI model for geotechnical engineering*. In the near term, it is safe to say that all ML/AI applications must quantify the uncertainty of the inference explicitly. A deterministic inference that does not reveal the underlying imprecision is certainly not trustworthy and susceptible to being labeled by the human user as a "hallucination". It is clear that ML/AI should be developed with the geotechnical context in mind such as complex geo-data attributes, site-specificity, and staged construction. The current literature on data-centric geotechnics already demonstrated value to practice. Solutions to MUSIC-3X data are possible. ML/AI is indispensable in "ML supremacy projects" but no Type 3 innovation that can create a big step change in value to practice has been proposed. Nonetheless, with the ongoing revolution in autonomous vehicles and robotics that may push AI to true intelligence (called AGI), Type 3 is a distinct possibility. In the author's opinion, the possible future scenarios that one can glimpse from some emerging technologies are already hugely impactful to practice. With this potential sea change as a backdrop, this perspectives article advocates researchers, engineers, and regulators to work in tandem to foster responsible innovation under the framing of "trustworthy data-centric geotechnics" that can comply with the EU AI Act. Our professional ethics that include safeguarding public interest require us to over-react to prepare ahead for a radically different future. It is timely to launch Geodata and AI (GEOAI) in 2024 to hothouse responsible innovations within and between geo-related disciplines to stay abreast of a "digital and connected intelligences everywhere" future.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Kok-Kwang Phoon: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization.

Data availability

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